

We made more than 3000 combinations by using the strains of *M. grisea* isolated from cultivated rice (*Oryza sativa* L.), common wild rice (*O. rufipogon*), goose grass (*Eleusine indica* Gaertn.), finger grass (*Digitaria sanguinalis* Scop.), and finger millet (*Eleusine coracana* Gaertn.) in Yunnan Province.

The results show that cross-fertility of strains isolated from upland rice is higher and wider than those isolated from lowland irrigated rice, but only one strain isolated from wild rice produced ascospores when crossed

with the strain isolated from lowland irrigated rice, and the mating type was MATI-1. Strains isolated from wild rice were crossed with strains isolated from goose grass, finger grass, and finger millet, too, but no ascospores were made in these combinations (Table 1).

Cross-fertility and pathogenicity of strains isolated from common wild rice were identical to those of strains isolated from rice (Table 2). We speculate that strains isolated from common wild rice are nearer to those isolated from cultivated rice than in other plants in cross-fertility and pathogenicity.

Fifteen hermaphroditic isolates have been found in Yunnan Province, and 13 of these have been isolated from upland rice. The hermaphroditic isolates of MATI-1 were crossed with the hermaphroditic isolates of MATI-2. Half the combinations produced mature perithecia, and 2-3% of the ascospores were viable. Through a series of backcrosses with field isolates, 20-30% viable ascospores were obtained. These field isolates and laboratory strains can be used in the study of inheritance of pathogenicity and the genetic analysis of avirulence in the fungus. ■

Performance of midland rice varieties in a blast hot spot

H. K. Ramappa, N. Shivakumar, N. M. Poonachha, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Ponnampet, Coorg District; and T. B. Anilkumar, Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya 571405, Karnataka, India

Blast (*Pyricularia oryzae*) is a major problem in almost all rice-growing areas in Karnataka, particularly in the high-rainfall malnad region where it is a major reason for low yields there. To find high-yielding, blast-resistant varieties, 27 rice genotypes were evaluated over 3 yr at ARS in Ponnampet, a hot spot for blast.

Thirteen midland varieties with the standard local variety Intan were sown on 10 Jun 1992, 22 Jun 1993, and 22 Jun 1994 and transplanted on 28 Jul 1992, 30 Jul 1993, and 29 Jul 1994, respectively. Heavy rainfall, a common occurrence, delayed transplanting. The genotypes were planted in a randomized complete block design in plots 10 × 7.5 × 9 m. Neck blast incidence was recorded twice during the grain development stage. The plot yields were converted to t ha⁻¹.

The mean neck blast incidence was significantly highest for Intan (69.37%), with the least incidence for IYT(SHW)91/10609 (see table). Among the varieties, mean yield was significantly lower for

Reaction of midland varieties to neck blast.^a ARS, Ponnampet, India. 1992-94.

Genotype	Neck blast incidence (%)				Rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
	1992	1993	1994	Mean	1992	1993	1994	Mean
IRLON90/18	9.77 ctg	9.67 cd	23.87 cd	14.43	3.9 ab	4.9 a	3.0 ab	3.9
KHP2	18.39 dct	12.32 cd	15.25 de	15.32	3.4 abc	3.0 bc	3.4 ab	3.3
IYT (SHW) 91/10609	3.71 g	5.14 d	8.22 e	5.69	3.1 bcd	2.8 cd	3.5 ab	3.1
IMRYT91/1708	20.33 ct	8.25 cd	7.08 e	11.89	2.9 cde	3.2 bc	3.4 ab	3.2
CTH6	0.83 fg	16.02 cd	9.72 e	11.19	4.2 a	1.6 atg	3.7 a	3.2
IET7/7191	22.50 cde	7.66 cd	13.17 de	14.44	2.3 def	3.1 bc	3.1 ab	2.8
RR12	16.23 dg	20.10 c	4.39 e	13.57	2.2 dg	2.7 cd	2.9 ab	2.6
KHRS55	28.40 bcd	37.26 b	14.63 de	26.76	2.9 cde	2.0 def	3.7 a	2.9
Jaya	21.67 cde	12.79 cd	16.72 de	17.06	2.0 cfg	2.3 cde	3.0 ab	2.4
IRLON90/140	15.38 dg	17.31 cd	6.90 c	13.20	2.0 cfg	1.9 dg	3.1 ab	2.3
Karna	40.41 b	67.64 a	31.57 c	46.54	1.2 g	1.3 fg	2.8 ab	1.8
KHRS26	33.45 bc	59.66 a	24.87 cd	39.33	1.4 fg	0.9 g	2.5 b	1.6
IRLON90/98	25.55 cd	14.12 cd	100.00 a	46.56	2.3 def	3.9 b	0.1 c	2.1
Intan	56.43 a	68.43 a	83.24 b	69.37	1.2 a	0.9 g	0.9 c	1.0
Mean of 3 yr			Blast incidence				Yield	
Comparison		SE	LSD (%)		SE	LSD (%)		
2 T × Y Mean		5.94	11.82		444.49	884.18		

^aWithin a column, figures followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

Intan, with the exception of Karna and KHRS26. In contrast, IRLON90/18 had a mean yield of 3915 kg ha⁻¹ and was on a par with KHP2, IYT(SHW)91/10609, IMRYT91/1708, and CTH6. Because IYT(SHW)91/10609 consistently had a low blast score and yielded the same as IRLON90/18, it should prove a good genotype for the midland region of Karnataka.

IRLON90/18 is a cross between BKNFR76106-16-0-1 and IR19961-131-

1-2, IYT(SHW)91/10609 is a cross between Ratna and ARC10659, and KHP2 is a cross between BG90-2 and IR8263-28-1. These genotypes—IRLON90/18, IYT(SHW)91/10609, IMRYT91/1708, and CTH6—consistently yielded more than 3 t ha⁻¹ under very high disease pressure over three seasons, making them extremely useful for Karnataka. Blast can cause up to 80% yield loss when the disease severity is 9. ■